

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation, Evaluation and Validation of Oral Film for The Treatment of Antimigraine by Using HPLC Method

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 21 June 2025

Keywords:

Oral film, Anti-migraine, HPLC, HILIC Mixed Mode, Zolmitriptan, HPMC, Super Disintegrator

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15709034

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was formulated, evaluate and validation of oral film by using HPLC. In the present study, the oral film of Zolmitriptan 5 mg was prepared by Solvent casting method using HPMC E-15 and HPMC E5 as a film forming polymer, Glycerin as a plasticizer, saccharin as a sweetening agent, Citric acid as a preservatives and Sodium starch glycolate is a super- disintegrator. Other formulation ingredients are also used in the formulation. Total five formulations (F1 to F5) were prepared by solvent casting method. Among these two formulations F4 show lower results and F5 show results on higher side. So, the formulations F5 were taken as optimize formulations in this study. The present study describes the development and validation of HPLC (HILIC) Mixed Mode method for determination of an Zolmitriptan. The separation was achieved by using ZIC-HILIC Mixed Mode (5 μ m; 150 x 4.6 mm ID.column by using solvent A; 15mM ammonium acetate solvent B; acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) as mobile phase with the flow rate of 0.9ml/min. Where detection was carried out by UV detector (SPD-10AVP) at 225nm. The retention time was found to be 4.23 min. The described method was linear over the range of 3.18 – 100 μ g/ml. The mean regression equation was found to be $y = 245511 + 428133x$, $R^2 = 0.9994$. The precision, ruggedness, accuracy, repeatability, robustness values were also within the prescribed limits. The developed HILIC Mixed Mode method was validated as per the ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Out of various methods, the oral route is the most preferred option for patients. Numerous pharmaceutical companies have focused their research on creating effective oral dosage

alternatives for paediatric, geriatric, noncompliant or nauseous patients. Advancements in oral drug delivery have progressed from basic conventional tablets and capsules to modified release forms, oral disintegrating tablets and most recently oral films.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Notably, pain, which is the primary symptom of the condition, is not always the most distressing aspect for all patients at all times. Migraine is characterized by a series of distinct phases often overlapping which include the prodromal (prodromal), aura, pain, and postdrome phases. Improved recognition of these phases has led to the understanding of migraine as a network disorder involving multiple regions of the cortex, subcortex, and brainstem, which together generate a wide range of signs and symptoms. We will explore these regions in detail in the upcoming sections, as they show altered function and structure in individuals with migraine and in animal models of the condition.^[1]

Defination of Migraine

A migraine is an intense headache characterized by pulsating, throbbing pain primarily on one side of the head. The headache phase of a migraine typically persists for several hours but can extend to an entire day. This pain often intensifies with physical activity, bright light, loud noises, and strong smells.

Types of Migraine

There are mainly two types:

1. Migraine with aura (Classic migraine)
2. Migraine without aura (Common migraine).

Migraine Symptoms

Changes in mood, trouble concentrating, sleep disturbances, fatigue, nausea, increased hunger, thirst and frequent urination, Muscle weakness, alterations in vision, ringing in the ear and heightened sensitivity to touch, sensitivity to light, sound and smells, Stiff neck, sensitivity to light or sound, difficulty concentrating, nausea and dizziness.

Diagnosis

1. When considering a migraine diagnosis
2. Establishing a migraine diagnosis
3. Focus on patient needs and education.^[2,3]

Oral Thin Film

They are also known as oral wafers. In recent years, oral thin films have emerged in the confectionery and oral care industries as oral strips. These innovative products have gained widespread acceptance among consumers for delivering vitamins and personal care items. Currently, oral films are recognized and validated technology for the systemic distribution of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) in over-the-counter (OTC) drugs and are in the initial to mid-development phases for prescription medications.

Fig 1: Oral film

Classification of Oral Films Consists of Three Types:

- Flash release/ Fast dissolving films (Placed on the tongue).
- Mucoadhesive melts away films (in the gingival or buccal region).

- Mucoadhesive sustained release films (adhere to the buccal mucosa).

ADVANTAGES

1. There is no need for a specially trained individual.
2. They are flexible, portable, making transportation and storage easier.
3. Dosing is accurately administered.
4. Enhanced stability and safety are achieved.
5. Each film contains a precise quantity of medication.
6. Rapid onset of action and improved bioavailability.
7. They provide a mouth freshening effect.
8. Patient adherence is improved.
9. Each film ensures accurate dose administration compared to liquid forms like drops or syrups.
10. Patients experiencing frequent vomiting, dysphagia, or motion sickness prefer this dosage form as they find it hard to swallow large volumes of water.
11. These films can be produced through cost-effective.

DISADVANTAGES

1. There are limitations on food and drink consumption.
2. Medications that require lower doses may be administered.
3. Special packaging is necessary for maintaining product stability and safety.
4. The variety of polymers available is limited.
5. The application of thin films can be constrained due to their low drug loading capacity when applying a less potent drug at high doses.
6. Typically, thin films are hygroscopic, so special care is needed for prolonged storage.
7. A larger surface area facilitates faster disintegration and dissolution in the oral cavity.

[4,5,6,7,8,9]

Manufacturing or Formulation Techniques of Oral Film

- A. Solvent casting method
- B. Semi-solid casting method
- C. Hot melt extrusion
- D. Solid dispersion extrusion
- E. Rolling method. [10,11,12]

Aim And Objective

Aim: Formulation, Evaluation and Validation of oral film for the treatment of antimigraine by using HPLC method

Objective:

- 1) To carry out the preformulation study of drug and formulation.
- 2) To formulate the oral film.
- 3) To evaluate the oral film.
- 4) To study the thickness, folding endurance, disintegration time, content uniformity and In vitro study of oral film.
- 5) To check the stability of oral film.
- 6) Simple, precise, accurate and economical HPLC method can be developed.
- 7) To increase the drug bioavailability, safety, effectiveness.
- 8) Validation of method according to ICH guideline.

Drug Profile

Fig 2: Zolmitriptan

1) **Synonyms /Chemical name:** Zolmitriptan, Zomig

2) **IUPAC Name:** (4S)-4-[[3-[2-(dimethylamino)ethyl]-1H-indol-5-yl]methyl]-1,3-oxazolidin-2-one

3) **Molecular Formula:** C₁₆H₂₁N₃O₂

4) **Molecular weight:** 287.3568 g/mol

5) **Color /Form:** Zolmitriptan is white to Cream, crystalline powder

6) **Odour:** Odourless

7) **Solubility:** Slightly soluble in water, freely soluble in methanol, dimethyl sulphoxide and dimethyl formamide soluble in ethanol, acetone and in isopropyl alcohol, slightly soluble chloroform, sparingly soluble in acetonitrile.

8) **Melting point:** 136 °C

9) **Category:** Antimigraine

10) **Mechanism of Action:** Zolmitriptan attaches with a high affinity to human 5-HT_{1B} and 5-HT_{1D} receptors, which leads to the constriction of cranial blood vessels. The therapeutic effect of zolmitriptan in treating migraine attacks is primarily due to its agonistic actions at the 5-HT_{1B/1D} receptors located on intracranial blood vessels (including the arteriovenous anastomoses) and sensory nerves of the trigeminal system, resulting in vasoconstriction and the suppression of pro-inflammatory neuropeptide secretion. ^[13,14]

Experimental Work / Condition

Preformulation Study

- To establish the necessary physicochemical characteristics of a new drug substance
- To determine its kinetic release rate profile

- To establish its compatibility with different Excipients.

Selection of Active Pharmaceutical Agents

Zolmitriptan, a serotonin receptor agonist of the 1B and 1D subtypes. It is a triptan, used in the acute treatment of migraine attacks with or without aura and cluster headaches. Zolmitriptan is available as a swallowable tablet, an oral disintegrating tablet, and a nasal spray. The usual dose of Zolmitriptan is 2.5 with a maximum dose of 15 mg in 24 h. The conventional tablet is administered 3 or 4 times a day due to its short biological half-life of about 2.5-3h, prolonged inpatient with hepatic impairment.

Results: For preparation and evaluation of oral film of Zolmitriptan was selected as active drug.

Organoleptic Properties

Confirmation or identification of drug was carried out by following methods.

- Color -White, crystalline powder
- Odour-Odourless
- Appearance - Amorphous Powder
- Taste - Bitter

Melting Point Determination

Melting point of Zolmitriptan was also measured in the laboratory and found to be in the range of 130-140°C.

Solubility Determination:

The solubility of pure drug in 10 mg/10 ml of solvent was carried out and it reveals that it was slightly soluble in water and freely soluble in methanol and ethanol (95%)

- Distilled water - Readily Soluble
- Methanol- Freely soluble

Procurement of Drug and Polymer

Drug: Zolmitriptan was received from Zydus Lifesciences Limited as a gift sample.

Polymer and other ingredients were used from research laboratory of college.

Table no 1: The General Formula for Formulation of oral Films Is Given Below

Sr. No	Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	Zolmitriptan	40mg	40mg	40mg	40mg	40mg
2	HPMC E15	150mg	150mg	150mg	150mg	180mg
3	HPMC E5	130mg	140mg	150mg	160mg	170mg
4	Citric acid	42mg	42mg	42mg	42mg	42mg
5	Saccharin	7mg	7mg	7mg	8mg	9mg
6	Sodium starch glycolate	20mg	25mg	27mg	28mg	30mg
7	Glycerine	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml
8	Methanol	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml

- 1) The final weight of the film = 50mg
- 2) Dimension (L×W) = 200cm × 180cm

Procedure For Preparation of Oral Film

1. The polymer (HPMC E15 and HPMC E5) are dissolved in methanol accurately weight and Transfer in glass beaker
2. Then dissolve properly with continuous stirring use magnetic stirrer.
3. Dissolve the API and other processing ingredients in methanol weight accurately and transfer into the another beaker and dissolve properly with continuous stirring.
4. Mix the above two solution to form a thick mass.
5. Taking the above thick mass and then transfer into the petri dish
6. Dry this film mass for 2- 3 days at room temperature.
7. After drying then remove thin film. And cut in above size.

8. Optimization of formulation same procedure is followed for all the formulation F1 to F5 and the formulation with all the acceptable properties and parameters to be selected.

Evaluation Parameter

For evaluation of psychophysical evaluation of the product, special controlled human taste panels are used.

1. Organoleptic evaluation

Appearance, Shape, and color

The formulated films were checked for their appearance, shape and color.

Table no 2 : The physical parameter of all the formulations

Formulation	Color	Shape
F1	Colorless	Rectangular
F2	Colorless	Rectangular
F3	Colorless	Rectangular
F4	Colorless	Rectangular
F5	Colorless	Rectangular

Form the above evaluation it is found that all the formulation so prepared are colorless and rectangular shape.

2. Thickness

Film thickness is crucial for ensuring drug content uniformity. Therefore, it is essential to measure the film's thickness at various key locations using a micrometer screw gauge or calibrated digital Vernier Calipers.

3. Weight Variation

The films underwent a mass variation study, where randomly selected films were weighed individually, and the average weight of five samples from each batch was calculated. This process was repeated for every batch.

4. Drug Content Uniformity

The films were tested for content uniformity The acceptable range for drug content uniformity. The film was cut, placed in 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol, the volume is made upto 100 ml with methanol. Solution was suitably diluted. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 225 nm. The range is 95% to 105%.

5. Folding endurance

Folding endurance refers to the number of times the film can be folded at the same location before any noticeable cracks appear, signifying film brittleness. This test was performed by repeatedly folding the film at the same point until a visible crack was observed, and the values were recorded.

6. Disintegration test

The disintegration of orally fast dissolving films is assessed using the USP disintegration apparatus. The recommended disintegration limit is 30

seconds or less for orally disintegrating tablets, which can also be applied to fast dissolving oral strips. Disintegration times may vary based on the formulation, generally ranging from 5 to 30 seconds. However, there is currently no official guidance specifically for oral fast disintegrating film strips.

7. In vitro drug release

For in-vitro dissolution studies, each film was carefully placed in a 50 ml glass beaker containing 25 ml of phosphate buffer at pH 6.8 using forceps. The dissolution medium temperature was maintained at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred at 50 rpm. Throughout the study, 3 ml aliquots were taken at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 minutes, and these were replaced with fresh buffer. The amount of drug released into the media was quantified using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-1800) at a wavelength of 225 nm.

8. Surface pH

To determine the surface pH of the films, each film was placed on a 1.5% w/v agar gel, followed by the application of pH paper (pH range 1-11) on top of the films. Any color change in the pH paper was noted and documented.

9. Stability studies

The optimized batch F5 was packed in a butter paper covered with aluminum foil and was isothermally stressed to study the stability under accelerated temperature and relative humidity conditions carried out at $40^\circ\text{C}/75\% \text{RH}$, $25^\circ\text{C}/60\% \text{RH}$ and $25^\circ\text{C}/40\% \text{RH}$ for a period of 2 months. Test samples were withdrawn every month and were subjected to various tests including visual inspection of the film, disintegration time and cumulative percent of drug release.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography:

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is currently one of the most effective instruments in analytical chemistry. It can separate, identify, and quantify the compounds found in any sample that can be dissolved in a liquid. Today, substances at trace levels as low as parts per trillion (ppt) can be readily detected. HPLC has been utilized in a wide range of samples, including pharmaceuticals, food products, nutraceuticals, cosmetics, environmental samples, forensic evidence, and industrial chemicals.

Instrumentation

The high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) of Shimadzu SCL-10AVP inbuilt with binary pump (LC-10ATVP), UV detector (SPD-10AVP), Rheodyne 20 μ l loop capacity manual injector (P/N 77251) was used throughout the analysis. The LC-Solution software was used to interpret the HPLC reports. Zic-HILIC Mixed Mode (5 μ m; 150 x 4.6 mm ID.) column was purchased from Ultrachrom Innovatives Pvt. Ltd was used throughout the analysis. Digital weighing balance (ME-204) purchased from Mettler-Toledo (USA), ultra-sonicator Labman[®] purchased from UltraChrom Ltd, India. Digital pH meter from Mettler-Toledo was purchased from (Mumbai-India). 50 μ micro-syringe was

purchased from Hamilton USA. 0.20 μ and 0.45 μ nylon membrane filters were purchased from Phenomenex[®] Mumbai, India.

Reagents And Reference Samples

The reference standard Zolmitriptan was purchased Zydus Lifesciences Limited. Ammonium acetate was purchased from Merck Ltd. (Mumbai-India) HPLC grade acetonitrile, methanol and HPLC grade water were purchased from Merck (Mumbai, India). 0.20 μ and 0.45 μ nylon membrane filters were used and purchased from Ultra Chrom Innovatives Pvt. Ltd. (India). All other chemicals and reagents were used of HPLC grade.

Standard and Sample Preparation

The Standard and sample solutions were prepared separately by dissolving standard and sample in a solvent mixture of Acetonitrile:Methanol:Water (20:40:40 v/v).

Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions

The chromatographic conditions were optimized by different analysis. (Using different column, different buffer and different modes of HPLC run, Table 3, Fig. a-d.

Table no 3. Method Development for HPLC Analysis of Zolmitriptan API

Trials	Column used	Mobile Phase	Mobile Phase composition	Flow Rate ml/Min	Observation
1	Zodiac C18 5 μ , (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15 mM Ammonium acetate- Acetonitrile;	50:50 v/v	0.8 ml/min	Separation time will be Different
2	Zodiac C18 5 μ , (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15 mM Ammonium acetate- Acetonitrile;	60:40 v/v	0.8 ml/min	Separation time will be Different s
3	Zodiac C18 5 μ , (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15 mM Ammonium acetate- Acetonitrile;	70:30 v/v	0.8 ml/min	Separation time will be Different
4	Zic-HILIC Mixed Mode(150 X 4.6 mm. ID.)	15 mM Ammonium acetate - Acetonitrile;	50:50 v/v	0.9 ml/min	Zolmitriptan separated as per the ICH guidelines.

Method Validation

In order to determine repeatability, a freshly prepared solution of Zolmitriptan was injected six times to evaluate the consistency of results, focusing on the relative standard deviation (RSD); the findings are displayed in Table 6. To establish both intra-day and inter-day precision of the method, Zolmitriptan was analyzed on a single day as well as over three separate days. The calculations for intra-day and inter-day precision are summarized in Table 7-8. The robustness of the method was tested by modifying chromatographic conditions, including changes in flow rates, mobile phases, and wavelengths. The robustness of the developed method is indicated by the overall standard deviation among the results under each varied condition, as shown in Table 9. Linearity was evaluated by injecting samples of different concentrations (100, 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.12 ppm), with the data represented in Table 10.

The accuracy of the prepared formulation was determined at 80%, 100%, and 120%, with results displayed in Table 11. The specificity of the proposed method was examined by analyzing a sample solution of Zolmitriptan. Ruggedness was determined using different analysts. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were determined from the linearity study. For system suitability, a freshly prepared solution of Zolmitriptan was injected six times to evaluate the closeness of results achieved for the relative standard deviation (RSD) in percentage.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result of Evaluation Parameter of Oral Film

Table no 4 : Evaluation Parameters of oral Film of Zolmitriptan

Sr no	Evaluation parameter	Evaluation of Formulation				
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	Appearance	Transparent	Transparent	Transparent	Transparent	Transparent
2	Thickness	0.30	0.29	0.27	0.21	0.20
3	Weight variation	0.090	0.092	0.110	0.085	0.080
4	%Drug Content (Sec+/-Sd)	87.14	86.62	90.57	95.14	97.57
5	Folding Endurance (Folds)	Does not comply	Does not comply	Does not comply	Complies	complies
6	Disintegration Time (Sec+/-)	45	50	49	35	31
7	In-Vitro Drug Release	93.47% in 10 min	95.72% in 10 min	95.31% in 10 min	97.47% in 10 min	97.72% in 10 min
8	Surface pH	6.12	6.19	6.33	6.52	6.59

Table no 5 : Stability Studies of oral Film

Sr.no	Time(days)	Appearance	In-vitro Disintegration time (sec)	%
1	Initial (0 Days)	Transparent and acceptable	32.4	98.5
2	1 Month (30 Days)	Transparent and acceptable	35.5	98.1
3	2 Months (60 Days)	Transparent and acceptable	30.8	98.7

Figure 3: Photograph of oral Film

Chromatographic condition: To establish a precise, linear, specific, and effective HPLC (HILIC-Hydrophilic Interaction Liquid Chromatography) Mixed Mode technique for the analysis of Zolmitriptan, various chromatographic conditions were tested, and the observed results are shown in Table 3 and Figs. 1a-d. There are

various columns available for HPLC, the Zic-HILIC Mixed Mode (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.) column was selected here due to its favourable peak shape, resolution, and absorbance. The Mobile Phase utilized was a mixture of 15mM Ammonium acetate and Acetonitrile in a 50:50 v/v in a ratio.

Fig a: Trial 1

Fig b: Trial 2

Fig c: Trial 3

Fig d: Trial 4

Fig 4: Repeatability Study

Fig 5: Intraday Study

Fig 6: Interday Study

Fig 7: Robustness Study: Flow Rate At 1.0 ml/min

Fig 8: Robustness Study: Flow Rate At 0.8 ml/min

Fig 9: Robustness Study: (52%)

Fig 10: Robustness Study: B (48 %)

Fig 11: Robustness Study: Wavelength 227 nm

Fig 12: Robustness Study: Wavelength 225 nm

Fig 13 : Calibration curve of Zolmitriptan

Fig 14 : Drug Accuracy (80%)

Fig 15 : Drug Accuracy (100%)

Fig 16 : Drug Accuracy Studies (120%)

Fig 17: Chromatogram of Ruggedness

Table 6: Repeatability Study of Zolmitriptan

Sr. No.	Drug Name; Zolmitriptan
	Peak Area; Conc. 100 ppm
1	24292312
2	24060477
3	24160210

4	24688506
5	24296753
6	24114023
Mean	24268714
STD. DEV.	226553.9433
RSD (%)	0.93

Table 7: Intraday Precision Data of Zolmitriptan

Drug Name: Zolmitriptan					
S. No.	Concentration (ppm)	Area	Average	Std. Deviation	%RSD
1	100 ppm	24292312	24171000	116293.51	0.48
	100 ppm	24060477			
	100 ppm	24160210			
2	100 ppm	24688506	24366427	293510.76	1.20
	100 ppm	24296753			
	100 ppm	24114023			
3	100 ppm	24284290	24117286	251583.05	1.04
	100 ppm	24239639			
	100 ppm	23827929			
Range of % RSD					0.48-1.20

Table 8: Interday/Intermediate Precision Data of Zolmitriptan

Drug Name: Zolmitriptan					
S. No.	Concentration (ppm)	Area	Average	Std. Deviation	%RSD
DAY 1	100 ppm	24284290	24117286	251583.05	1.04
	100 ppm	24239639			
	100 ppm	23827929			
DAY 2	100 ppm	23075500	23201035	109291.19	0.47
	100 ppm	23274998			
	100 ppm	23252606			
DAY 3	100 ppm	23204604	23244695	42616.54	0.18
	100 ppm	23289453			
	100 ppm	23240029			
Range of % RSD					0.18-1.04

Table 9: Robustness data of Zolmitriptan

Variables	Zolmitriptan			
	t _R (min)	k'	T _f	N
Flow rate (+0.1 mL/min)	3.75	0.65	1.42	2217
Flow rate (-0.1 mL/min)	4.63	0.63	1.43	2283
Solvent B (+2%)	4.14	0.65	1.43	2279
Solvent B (-2%)	4.11	0.64	1.45	2225
Wavelength (+2°C)	4.17	0.73	1.43	2272
Wavelength (-2°C)	4.17	0.73	1.43	2272
Mean ± S.D.	4.16±0.28	0.67±0.05	1.43±0.01	

Table 10: Linearity Data of Zolmitriptan

Name of Drug Zolmitriptan		
Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/mL)	Area
1	3.125	624944
2	6.25	1244242
3	12.5	2504457
4	25	5475381
5	50	11624904
6	100	24292312

Regression Equation	$y = 245511x + 428133$
Correlation coefficient (R^2)	0.9994
Std. error of intercept	142842.9627
Std. Dev. Of intercept	349892.372
LOQ	14.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
LOD	4.28 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

Table 11 : Accuracy data of Zolmitriptan

Drug Name: Zolmitriptan			Drug content: 5 mg		Developed formulation:		
Std. conc. (%)	Std. (ppm)	Peak area	Drug (%)	Drug (ppm)	Peak area	Avg. peak area	Drug Rec. (%)
100%	100 ppm	24292312	80	79.90	18009040	18355000	94.45
				80	18300500		
				80.10	18700960		
			100	99.90	24036227	24407963.5	100.48
				100	24292312		
				100.10	24779700		
			120	119.90	28404064	28691766.5	98.43
				120	28584055		
				120.10	28799478		
Drug recovery Range (%) as per ICH = 100±10%							94.45 % - 100.48 %

Repeatability: The calculated RSDs for the tested Zolmitriptan were below 2%, which is significant according to ICH guidelines.

Precision: The results from the intraday precision studies ranged from 0.48% to 1.20%, with peaks showing %RSD not exceeding 2%, in line with system suitability standards, confirming the precise of the method. The interday precision studies yielded results between 0.18% and 1.04%, with peaks also displaying %RSD not exceeding 2%, consistent with system suitability, further confirming the method precise.

Robustness: The overall %RSD of the results with changes in flow, wavelength and mobile phase composition remained within acceptance criteria, demonstrating that the method is robust to slight changes in internal parameters, thus justifying its robustness.

Linearity: The correlation coefficient was observed to be within acceptance criteria, confirming the method's linearity and justifying the findings based on the graph.

Accuracy: The mean recovery percentage of Zolmitriptan 5mg film was observed to fall within acceptance criteria, ranging from 94.45% to 100.48%, with %RSD of recovery also within acceptable limits, thereby confirming accuracy.

Specificity: The analysis indicates that the analyte's peak was pure, thus confirming the specificity of the method.

Ruggedness: A comparison with the optimized chromatogram indicated that the method remained stable when performed by different analysts.

LOD/LOQ: They were found to be LOD 4.28 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and LOQ 14.25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

System Suitability Testing:

Table 12: Represents The System Suitability Studies for Zolmitriptan.

Test Criteria	Results	Acceptance criteria
Theoretical plates (N)	2052	≥ 2000

Capacity Factor (K')	0.748	≤ 0.5
Tailing factor (T)	1.49	< 1.5
Retention time (t_R)	4.23 min.	$> k'$
Wavelength (nm)	225 nm	> 200 nm
Repeatability (% RSD)	0.93	$< 2\%$
Intra-Day Precision (% RSD)	0.48-1.20	$< 2\%$
Inter-Day Precision (% RSD)	0.18-1.04	$< 2\%$
Linearity range	3.18 – 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	NA
Regression equation	$Y = 245511x + 428133$	NA
Correlation Coefficient (r^2)	0.9994	NA
SE of intercept (Se)	142842.9627	NA
SD of intercept (Sa)	158658.6856	NA
LOQ ^a ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	14.25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	NA
LOD ^a ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	4.28 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	NA

Summary

Analysis of any product is very important to assure to assume the quality of product followed by safety and efficacy. Its plays very important role in the medicinal field. To assume desired quality of the product analysis is very important. There are some chromatographic method have been reported for the determination of Zolmitriptan single dosage form. Following method have been developed for the determination of Zolmitriptan. Analytical method development and validation of antimigraine drug. A new HILIC Mixed Mode method was developed for the determination of Zolmitriptan. The separation was achieved by using Zic-HILIC Mixed Mode, 5 μ , (150 X 4.6 mm. ID.). column by using solvent A : 15 mM ammonium acetate solvent B : acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) as mobile phase with the flow rate of 0.9 ml/min. Where detection was carried out by UV detector (SPD-10AVP) at 225 nm. The retention time was found to be 4.23 min. The system suitability test shows the response with retention time, theoretical plate, tailing factor and peak area. Validation of the proposed method was carried out according to ICH guidelines. The developed

method was validated by various parameters like Accuracy, Precision, Linearity and LOD & LOQ, Specificity, Robustness and Ruggedness. Repeatability was performed and % RSD was found 0.93. Linearity was found over the range 3.18 to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. the mean regression equation was found to be $y=245511x + 428133$, $R^2: 0.9994$. LOD and LOQ was found to be 4.28 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 14.25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. Precision study of Zolmitriptan was determined by the peak area. The intraday and intraday precision study were carried out. The % RSD of intraday was found in range of 0.48-1.20% and interday is 0.18-1.04%. It is under the limit that is not more than 2%. Recovery study was carried out in the range of 80%, 100%, 120%. It gives the response within the limit. The % recovery found to be 94.45 % - 100.48 %. Specificity was carried out and the peak of analyte was pure and it confirmed the specificity of the method. Ruggedness was carried out by different analyst no changes are found while analysis.

CONCLUSION

Oral drug delivery is considered to be an important alternative to the oral route for the systemic administration of drugs, as it considered the most convenient, easy, safest route of administration. Oral mucosa has offers better permeability to many drugs and it act as an excellent site for the absorption of drugs. Oral thin film is used as a novel approach, as it dissolve rapidly in mouth and directly reaches to the systemic circulation. Oral film technology fulfils all the requirements of potential solid dosage form. In the present study, the oral film of Zolmitriptan 5 mg was prepared by Solvent casting method using HPMC E-15 and HPMC E5 as a film forming polymer, Glycerine as a plasticizer, saccharin as a sweetening agent, Citric acid as a preservatives and Sodium starch glycolate is a super- disintegrator. Other formulation ingredients are also used in the formulation. Total five formulations (F1 to F5) were prepared by solvent casting method. The strategy for formulation development was to optimize the concentration of polymer HPMC E15 and HPMC E5 at which all the evaluation parameters and percent drug content would be in

limit. The stripes was evaluated for various parameters like colour, size & shape, pH, disintegration time, thickness, folding endurance test. All the strips were colourless and rectangular in shape, based on % drug content the formulations F1, F2, F3 failed in the test, so the formulations F4 and F5 were to be taken into consideration. Among these two formulations F4 show lower results and F5 show results on higher side. So, the formulations F5 were taken as optimize formulations in this study. All the formulations passed the pH, DT and thickness folding endurance test. From the present study, it is concluded that the optimum level of polymer in the oral film and orally disintegrating strip formulation should be as high as 50%-60% to pass all the tests and drug content too. The developed HILIC Mixed Mode method was found to be linear over concentration range. Therefore, the developed HILIC Mixed Mode method can be applied for routine quantitative and qualitative analysis of Zolmitriptan. The developed HILIC Mixed Mode method was validated as per the ICH guidelines.

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HOW TO CITE: Sohan Thipe*, Shraddha Muneshwar, Shailesh Jawarkar, Formulation, Evaluation and Validation of Oral Film for The Treatment of Antimigraine by Using HPLC Method, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 2864-2879. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709034>

